

TEACHING PERSONNEL IN HIGHER EDUCATION PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Jumanyozova T.A.
Bakhtiyarova A.M.

Urganch Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy
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ANNOTATION

The article describes the appearance of a modern teacher, important features of the teacher's activity, pedagogical ethics and talent.

Keywords: pedagogic ethics pedagoga, pedagogic creativity, pedagogic creativity, pedagogue, lichnostnye kachestva pedagoga

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Education and pedagogical activity. It is aimed at organizing the educational process in higher education in accordance with the requirements of society. The educational process in higher education is characterized by an organic combination of educational and research aspects, an increase in the role of student activity and independent work, and the creative potential of an individual. Pedagogical activity of the higher school combines theoretical and practical activities [2,7]. Theoretical activity is related to the discovery of new patterns. Practical activity is aimed at changing certain situations and solving the system of pedagogical tasks. By the term pedagogue, we mean an employee who has his own opinion, judgments, signs of relativity and subjectivity. He may not be able to treat everyone equally

But everyone needs to be convinced that he is a fair pedagogue who strives to do good to all students with an impartial intention. The reputation of a teaching staff is the influence recognized by all, acquired due to his deep knowledge of his field, high moral qualities, life experience, active participation in scientific research and public works. Pedagogical activity has a creative nature by its essence, creativity is needed only when a person faces a problem. Pedagogical activity is related to the main essence of pedagogical creativity with such characteristics, the purpose and character of pedagogical activity. Pedagogical activity is an action aimed at the process of solving endless pedagogical issues based on the

common goal of forming a person's personality, worldview, belief, mind, and behavior[1,2,5].

Modern science and technology development requires the pedagogue to be creative, to be able to think freely about the important problems of his field, to be able to convey the achievements of the field to students. This moral belief is visible in the teacher's moral influence in the process of teaching, in educational work, in his relations with students and others, in his behavior, in his daily lifestyle. Pedagogical ethics means humanism, fairness, conscientiousness, honesty, doing good, etc., in relation to pedagogical activities. In the theory of ethics, goodness is considered the most important category, doing good is a positive moral

virtue, it reflects the ideal of normative ethics, the content of positive moral qualities in individual ethics is the sum of positive attitudes towards human activities or actions. Goodness is a concept that reflects the unity of the interests of the society and the individual in the mind and moral practice of a person, benefits the society and the individual, and is compatible with social development[1,8].

In pedagogical ethics, the concept of goodness is determined in connection with the teacher's activity. The pedagogue determines the goals and tasks of teaching a certain subject together with other subjects, thinks about the content of teaching, modern forms and methods that help to activate the student's educational and cognitive activity. A distinctive feature of the teacher's educational and pedagogical activity is his active participation in scientific and research work. When describing the pedagogical activity of a secondary school teacher, teaching is usually based on the researches of N. V. Kuzmina and Z. F. Esareva, who distinguish the following components in this structure - constructive; organizational; gnostic; communicative. The constructive component is manifested in the form of design or constructive skills in research, education, educational work. Design skills are intellectual skills for modeling research or learning. The design skills of the university teacher were studied, such activity is manifested in the ability to clearly plan, research and build the educational process. This is the interdependent activity of the teacher, student and other scientists [2,7].

Organizational activity consists of the ability to organize yourself and your time; individual, group, collective work of students; selection of personnel for collective research, division of tasks. The main task of organizational activity is to combine the efforts of all participants of the activity.

Researchers consider the pedagogical task as a special type of system that is the main unit of the pedagogical process. V. A. Slastenin understands the pedagogical task as a meaningful pedagogical situation for the purpose of knowing and changing reality [1,4,6].

There are three large groups of pedagogical tasks in the targeted activity of a teacher: strategic, tactical and operational. Strategic goals are derived from the overall goal of education. Set externally, they reflect the objective needs of social development.

These tasks determine the initial goals and final results of pedagogical activity. In the actual pedagogical process, strategic tasks are transformed into tactical tasks. Tactical tasks are related to one or another stage of solving strategic tasks, focusing on the final result of education.

Operational tasks are urgent, urgent tasks that the teacher solves in his practical work. The analysis of the professional activity of a university teacher shows that this profession is the most difficult and the most creative [2,8].

It includes specific tasks of the pedagogue's work and the educational process while maintaining the content of the concept of pedagogue's responsibility. The pedagogue should give the student in-depth theoretical and practical knowledge, prepare him for life and work. In addition, it is necessary for the student to determine the existing abilities and skills of young people, to be in personal relationships, and to cultivate the positive moral qualities that exist in them. Pedagogical orientation includes: student-centeredness; focus on oneself; focusing on the subject side of the teaching profession [1,4,5]. Participation of a teacher in communication with other people means ease of communication with the interlocutor, adequacy, ability to observe the interlocutor's reaction, react to it and enjoy communication.

The teacher's ability to establish long-term and mutually effective relationships with students is related to communication skills.

Communicative skills are communication skills that act in a unique way in the field of pedagogical interaction. A teacher who performs pedagogical activities skillfully explains the educational and educational aspects of the lesson and transforms the skills of changes in nature and society into skills in the worldview of children's activities. Understanding faith, manners, and civic duty is one of the main qualities of a teacher. Awareness of social

activity and civic duty is a characteristic characteristic of a pedagogue, and a real pedagogue is a public figure in the full sense and shows students a practical example of being socially active in life[3,6,7]. An important quality of a pedagogue is the ability to quickly compromise with people, enterprisingness, cordiality, which represents the high culture of dealing in him. Because the pedagogue always has to communicate with students and work with them. Success in the work of a teacher is ensured by the ability to communicate with students, certain groups and individuals in their daily activities. Pedagogical etiquette is a professional-ethical feature expressed in the pedagogue's relationship with students, the team of pedagogues, parents and public representatives, combining the categories, rules and norms of universal morality with the features appropriate to the educational process

A pedagogue should learn the norms of pedagogical ethics, apply them in practice, compare them with his own world view and moral experience. As a result of thinking and feeling, trying in life, the rules of pedagogical ethics become the pedagogue's own beliefs, aspirations, and moral qualities. Pedagogical activity is the labor activity of people who are responsible to the people, to the state, specially prepared to educate students in order to prepare the young generation for life and work [2,3,7].

To work successfully, every teacher must have pedagogical skills. The owner of pedagogical skill achieves high results with little effort, creativity is always his partner. Pedagogical skill can be acquired only by someone who is capable and talented in pedagogical work. Ability appears and develops in the process of activity. Ability is different from competence and competence. If the result of training and study is calculated as a result of skill and perseverance, it is also necessary to have anatomic-physiological characteristics of ability and mind, that is, in the human nervous system. It is on this natural ground that the mental quality called ability develops [3,7]. In order for the pedagogical activity to be effective, the teacher must have the following types of abilities. The ability to know is the ability to relate to relevant fields of science - mathematics, physics, biology, literature, etc. A teacher with this ability knows the subject not only in the scope of the training course, but much more deeply, he always follows the discoveries in the field of his subject, he knows the material from thread to needle, he is extremely interested in it, he also performs simple research [3,4 ,8]

Speech ability is the ability to clearly and clearly express one's thoughts

and feelings with the help of speech and gestures. This is very important for the teaching profession. The speech of the teacher is always aimed at the students. Even if the teacher is explaining a new lesson, analyzing or criticizing the student's answer, his speech is always distinguished by his inner strength, confidence, and interest in what he is talking about [1,3,6]. The expression of his opinion will be clear, simple and understandable for students. Organizational ability means, firstly, the ability to organize, unite a group of students, inspire them to solve important tasks, and secondly, organize their work correctly. Organizing one's

work means being able to properly plan and control work. Experienced teachers have the characteristic of being able to allocate time correctly, and to reach the set deadline. The ability to gain reputation is to have a direct emotional and volitional influence on students and to gain reputation on this basis. Reputation is gained not only on this basis, but also on the basis of the teacher's good knowledge, kindness, gentleness, etc

This ability refers to the totality of the teacher's personal qualities, such as his willpower, courage, endurance, etc., as well as the belief that he has the right to feel the responsibility of teaching and educating students, and the ability to convey this belief to students. depending [2,5,7,8]. The ability to deal correctly means to be able to approach children, to be able to establish very effective relations with them from the pedagogical point of view, and the presence of pedagogical delicacy. The ability to see the future is expressed in the ability to see the consequences of one's actions, the ability to imagine what kind of person the student will be in the future, and the ability to predict what qualities should be developed in the student. The ability to distribute attention is explained by the development of all characteristics of attention, size, strength, visibility, ability to will, mobilization for the teacher [1,4,8]. The correct organization of pedagogical work, that is, educational work, is not only economically important, but also of great importance in increasing the quality of education and improving it. Correct and cost-effective organization of activities creates comfort for the person himself and for the people working with him.

The uniqueness of the teacher's work is its versatility and complexity [2,5]. At the same time, this work has a creative character, that is, it not only creates something new, but also changes in content. Every situation, relationship with students is different and unrepeatable in a certain sense in every conscious teacher. The area in which the teacher works - the student also changes physically, mentally and spiritually. The difficulty and complexity of the teacher's work, the subtlety of dealing with the student, influencing him, require him to have a deep knowledge of the theory of education and the science of psychology. The versatility of a teacher's work can be seen in the time spent on it. The complexity of education is characterized by an increase in the amount of time spent on teacher's work. This causes the border between the teacher's work and free time to disappear more and more. Another feature of a teacher's work is that it is always carried out under the supervision and supervision of teachers. As the teacher educates the students, the types of his activities are constantly changing [2]. The increasing complexity of educational work complicates the teacher's task and expands the field of activity. The teacher is approaching the level of a research scientist who acquires knowledge and then teaches it to young people, the teacher is acquiring the characteristics of a researcher of the children's community, a sensitive psychologist, a theoretician and a practitioner as an educator. The goal of the teacher is not to discover new things for science, to make a complete scientific contribution to the theory of pedagogy, but to find effective methods and tools of education by deeply analyzing his own and others' advanced experience.

Creativity of teachers plays the role of a chain connecting scientific pedagogical research and educational experience. The work experience of advanced schools shows that a real scientific and valuable pedagogical work can be created due to this connection, and the pedagogical conclusions and recommendations in such a work will be acceptable to many people and will make a significant contribution to the improvement of

education in schools. A teacher's creativity is always based on a certain experience. Because a creative person must strive for something. The teacher refers to the achievements of pedagogy, psychology and educational methodology, looking for ways to acquire advanced methods and methods and apply them in his work. Because a creative teacher does not directly accept the experience of others without analysis, but compares it to his own experience. Only then will he accept its new aspects. Therefore, creativity is not a trait, but a product of a teacher's long work and high pedagogical culture. Teaching is an honorable but difficult profession. To become a good teacher, it is not enough to acquire pedagogical theory. Because the pedagogical theory describes the general laws and rules, generalized methodical ideas about teaching and educating children. Attention to young individual characteristics of teachers is emphasized.

There are situations that do not correspond to the pedagogical theory. This requires the teacher to have extensive knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills and creativity. That is why a teacher working in a general education school of the independent state of Uzbekistan: - Able to teach, creative, business-minded; - Perfectly mastered national culture and universal human values, worldly knowledge, well-versed in religious sciences, spiritually mature; - Every citizen who believes in the development of Uzbekistan as an independent state, who correctly understands his patriotic duty, who has excellent knowledge of the field, psychological, pedagogical knowledge and skills, as well as theoretical sciences, who loves the profession of pedagogue and students. It is necessary for a student to be a good person, to be able to think freely and creatively, to be demanding, fair and polite [3].

Thus, the teacher's pedagogical skill is determined by the high level of solving pedagogical tasks, the synthesis of the teacher's personal qualities, his knowledge and skills in various fields of scientific and pedagogical activity.

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